

ANALYSIS OF BI-STABILITY AND RESIDUAL STRESS RELAXATION IN HYBRID UNSYMMETRIC LAMINATES

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Abstract:

Unsymmetric bi-stable composite laminates are receiving interests in adaptive and deployable structures. The low load-bearing capacity and the residual stress relaxation of such laminates are significant limitations for application. The hybridization of unsymmetric composite laminates has potential to solve the problem. In this paper, the hybrid bi-stable laminates are investigated by analytical, finite element and experimental techniques. The curvature decrease of hybrid laminates along with the residual stress relaxation in the polymer matrix is investigated. The critical snap-through loads of hybrid laminates are numerically and experimentally studied. The improved critical load of hybrid laminate and the limited over time reducing of critical load are discussed. Comparisons of cured shape and critical loads between hybrid and pure bi-stable laminates show that the hybridization enable to accomplish both the high load-bearing capacity, the large shape change and the limited response to the residual stress relaxation in the polymer matrix.

Keywords: *Unsymmetric laminate; Hybrid composites; Bi-stable*

1. Introduction

There have been a lot of works on the generation of bi-stable unsymmetric fiber reinforced composite laminates. When cooled down to room temperature, unsymmetric laminates which are sufficiently wide and thin, deform into two possible stable configurations with almost cylindrical shape.

However, it is needed to overcome several shortcomings in relying upon laminate asymmetry to produce the required curvatures^[1]. Such as the restrictive geometries determined by the stacking sequences and the negative influences of moisture effect^[2]. One interesting idea recently to emerge is the hybridization of unsymmetric laminates that can give more design freedom of cured curvatures^[3], in which an analytical study on cured shape of hybrid bi-stable laminates were proposed^[4]. It is possible to accomplish a series of bi-stable laminates which have continuous curvature change, by the design of metal layer. In this paper, both the analytical and finite element methods are developed to predict the cured shape of hybrid composite laminates. How the metal ply contributes to the bi-stability of hybrid laminates is analyzed. The influence of moisture effect on hybrid laminate and pure fiber reinforced laminate is compared and

discussed. The critical snap through load of hybrid laminate is predicted by FEA. The influence of moisture effect on hybrid laminate and pure fiber reinforced laminate is compared and discussed. In the end, the advantages of hybrid laminate comparing with pure fiber reinforced laminate are summarized.

2. Analytical model

The Rayleigh-Ritz method is widely used to predict bi-stable unsymmetric laminates' cured shape. As with the application of minimum energy principles to any problem, stable equilibrium shapes are found by minimizing the total potential energy, Π , given by^[5-8]

$$\Pi = \int_v \omega dV \quad (1)$$

$$\omega = \frac{1}{2} C_{ij} \varepsilon_i \varepsilon_j - \beta_i \varepsilon_i \Delta T \quad (2)$$

Where: ω represents the strain energy density. C_{ij} denote the material elastic constants. β_i are the coefficients related to the elastic constants and thermal expansion coefficients. ε_i are the strains. ΔT is the difference in temperature.

For unsymmetric laminates, the thermally induced directional deformation of the single layer results in

large out-of-plane deformation. To take into account the large deformation which are often many times over the laminate thickness, the linear strain–displacement relations must be extended by non-linear terms. It is assumed that the laminate obeys the Kirchhoff hypothesis, and that hypothesis is used in conjunction with the von Karman approximation to the geometrical nonlinear strain-displacement relations^[8-10]:

$$\begin{aligned}\varepsilon_x &= \frac{\partial u^0}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w^0}{\partial x} \right)^2 - z \frac{\partial^2 w^0}{\partial x^2} \\ \varepsilon_y &= \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w^0}{\partial y} \right)^2 - z \frac{\partial^2 w^0}{\partial y^2} \\ \varepsilon_{xy} &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u^0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial w^0}{\partial x} \frac{\partial w^0}{\partial y} \right) - z \frac{\partial^2 w^0}{\partial x \partial y}\end{aligned}\quad (3)$$

Where the index 0 refers to the laminate neutral plane, where u^0 and v^0 are the x- and y-reference-surface displacements, w^0 is the z-displacement. ε_x , ε_y and ε_{xy} are the total strains.

Substituting equation (3) into equation (2) and (1), total potential energy of the laminate is given by^[9]

$$\begin{aligned}\Pi &= \int_V \left(\frac{1}{2} \bar{Q}_{ij} \varepsilon_i \varepsilon_j - \beta_i \varepsilon_i \Delta T \right) dV \\ &= \int_{-L_x/2}^{L_x/2} \int_{-L_y/2}^{L_y/2} \int_{-H/2}^{H/2} \left(\frac{1}{2} Q_{11} \varepsilon_x^2 + Q_{12} \varepsilon_x \varepsilon_y + Q_{16} \varepsilon_x \varepsilon_x + \frac{1}{2} Q_{22} \varepsilon_y^2 + Q_{26} \varepsilon_y \varepsilon_y \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{2} Q_{66} \varepsilon_{xy}^2 - (Q_{11} \alpha_x + Q_{12} \alpha_y + Q_{16} \alpha_{xy}) \varepsilon_x \Delta T - \right. \\ &\quad \left. (Q_{12} \alpha_x + Q_{22} \alpha_y + Q_{26} \alpha_{xy}) \varepsilon_y \Delta T - \right. \\ &\quad \left. (Q_{16} \alpha_x + Q_{22} \alpha_y + Q_{66} \alpha_{xy}) \varepsilon_x \Delta T \right) dx dy dz\end{aligned}\quad (4)$$

Where, L_x and L_y are the side lengths of the laminate and H is the laminate thickness. In Eq. (4), the Q terms represent the transformed reduced stiffness, α is the thermal expansion coefficient.

A practical way to solve this problem is the use of approximate expressions for both curvatures and strain-displacement relations, as functions of unknown coefficients. Geometrical assumptions for the out-of-plane displacements of hybrid unsymmetric laminates lead to the general second-order approach

$$w(x, y) = \frac{1}{2} (a_0 x^2 + b_0 y^2) \quad (5)$$

Where, the coefficients a_0 and b_0 represent the curvatures in the x- and y-directions respectively. Both curvatures are assumed constant throughout the plate.

For the description of the in-plane deformations,

several approximations can be found in the literature^[9, 11-14]. The robustness and reliability of the modeling framework depend on the scaling and conditioning number of the system of solving equations. A high order complete polynomial approximating to the displacement field has been proposed by Pirrera and Cerami^[15, 16]. They carried out calculations at orders 3, 5, 7, 9 and showed that increasing orders do not lead to major differences in the bifurcation diagram. Actually, by respecting the essential boundary conditions and imposing symmetries, this number can be reduced. Here, the mid-plane displacements are approximated by using the following polynomials with 14 unknown coefficients:

$$\begin{aligned}u^0 &= a_1 x + a_2 y + a_3 xy + a_4 x^2 y + a_5 xy^2 + a_6 x^3 + a_7 y^3 \\ v^0 &= b_1 x + b_2 y + b_3 yx + b_4 y^2 x + b_5 yx^2 + b_6 y^3 + b_7 x^3\end{aligned}\quad (6)$$

substituting the displacement approximations (5) and (6) into the strain displacement relation (3) and substituting the resulting expressions into (4), the total potential energy of the laminate becomes a function which is dependent on the coefficients a_m , b_m ($m=0,1,\dots,7$).

The principle of the minimum total potential energy requires the first variation of Π to be zero:

$$\delta \Pi = \frac{\delta \Pi}{\delta a_m} \delta a_m + \frac{\delta \Pi}{\delta b_m} \delta b_m = 0 \quad (7)$$

To satisfy this condition, every summand in equation (7) must be zero, which results in a coupled non-linear algebraic equation system. The equation group is solved with specially-written mathematical software. These solutions should be checked for their stability by means of $\delta^2 \Pi$, which has to be positive and definite for a stable deformation state.

3 Finite Element Method

In addition to analytical method, Finite Element Method (FEM) is a robust way to study the bi-stable laminates. The commercial finite element code ABAQUS is widely employed to predict the cured shape. A cool-down analysis is used to predict the equilibrium cured shapes of bi-stable laminates. The physical process itself takes a considerable time to complete (a few hours depending on the curing cycle that the material requires) and therefore it can be considered as a quasi-static process. In FEA, the

laminates is modeled using the four-node-square shell elements (S4R), and the model is clamped at the center point. An initial temperature of the elevated curing temperature is applied on the model in the initial step, and in the ‘*Static’ analysis step the temperature of the model decreases to a final room temperature^[17]. At the end of the ‘*Static’ analysis step, the stable states of the hybrid bi-stable laminates are obtained.

After the cool-down simulation, the snap-through simulation of the bi-stable configurations can be conducted. The snap-through problem of unsymmetric laminates is a buckling problem in essence. This problem has to be solved either dynamically or with the aid of artificial damping. The STABILIZE technique in ‘Static’ analysis introduces artificial damping to deal with local instability and also perform the pseudo dynamic analysis for the snap through process.

4. Experimental procedure

Within the current research, several experimental studies have been carried out on hybrid laminates made of CFRP and Steel. The materials and their properties are given in Table 1.

Two CFRP-metal hybrid laminates were manufactured with the layup [0/st/90] (0.23 mm steel)

and dimensions of 300 × 100mm, whose bi-stable shapes are shown in Fig. 1. The other four laminates were manufactured with the layups [0/st/90] (0.37mm steel and 100 × 100mm), [0/st/90] (0.23mm steel and 80 × 80mm), [0/90] (300 × 100mm) and [0/0/90/90] (300 × 100mm), see Fig.2. The laminates were autoclave manufactured at the cured temperature 170 °C and cooled to the room temperature 20 °C. The curvatures of the two shapes were measured. In order to study the influence of the moisture effect, the curvatures of different laminates are measured again at the 15th day after the manufacturing process. The snap through load is measured, the bi-stable laminate is placed on a smooth glass plate and load is applied at the central point of laminates, see Fig.3.

Table 1 Thermo-mechanical properties of CFRP and metal layer

CFRP	$E_{11}=137.47$ GPa, $E_{22}=10.07$ GPa, $G_{12}=7.17$ GPa, $\nu_{12}=0.23$, $\alpha_{11}= 0.37 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\alpha_{22} = 24.91 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$, thickness=0.125mm
Steel	$E_m=200$ GPa, $\nu_{12}=0.23$, $\alpha_m=12 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$, thickness=0.23mm and 0.37mm

Fig.1 Two stable shapes of hybrid bistable laminates

Fig.2 Manufactured laminates

Fig3. Illustration of loading at the central point of laminates

5 Results and Discussion

The curvatures of five bi-stable laminates from experiments, analytical expressions and finite element analysis are given in Fig.4. The experimental data were measured immediately after the manufacture process. The comparisons in Fig.4 show a good agreement among the experiments, analytical model and finite element simulation. The cured curvature of the pure T300/Epoxy laminate with the layup [0/90] is 12.3 m^{-1} , while the cured curvature with the layup [0/0/90/90] is 6.02 m^{-1} . The result demonstrates that the cured curvature decreases greatly as the layers increase. It is difficult for pure bi-stable composite laminates to have other curvatures because the thickness of the prepreg is often normalized. The hybrid laminate with layups [0/st/90] deforms to be a cylindrical shell with a curvature of 6.14 m^{-1} , which is almost the same as the

curvature of the [0/0/90/90] laminate.

The thermal strain mismatch between composite plies is the main reason of bi-stability for pure composite laminate. For the hybrid composite laminate, the metal ply also has large thermal strain after cooling down. To identify the main role of giving rising to bi-stability, an assumption that the thermal coefficients of composite plies are zero is made. FEM is employ to calculate the shapes of hybrid composite laminates in Fig.2 again based on the assumption. The results are presented in Table 2. It indicates that the curvatures of the hybrid laminates decrease little even the thermal strain of composite plies are ignored. So, it is concluded that the thermal strain of the metal ply plays the main role of giving rise to the bi-stability.

Table 2 FEM calculated curvatures of hybrid laminates with the assumption of zero thermal coefficients for composite plies and the curvature decrease comparing with normal hybrid laminates

Hybrid laminate	0/st/90 300×100mm 0.23mm st	0/st/90 80×80mm 0.23mm st	0/st/90 100×100mm 0.37mm st
Curvature m^{-1}	5.43	5.43	3.22
Curvature Decrease	15.5%	15.5%	13.4%

Table 3 Experimental measured curvatures of hybrid laminates and pure bi-stable laminates at the 15th day after the manufacturing process and the curvature decrease comparing with the original curvatures.

Bi-stable laminate	0/st/90 300×100mm 0.23mm st	0/st/90 80×80mm 0.23mm st	0/st/90 100×100mm 0.37mm st	0/0/90/90 300×100mm	0/90 300×100mm
Curvature m^{-1}	5.89	5.76	3.58	3.25	7.47
Curvature Decrease	4.53%	4.16%	3.76%	46.01%	39.47%

Fig. 4 Cured curvatures of different laminates

For a pure unsymmetric laminate, the residual thermal stress will continuously decrease because of the moisture effect of polymer matrix and the elongation of molecule chain of polymer matrix. And then results in continuous decreasing of laminate curvature. However for a hybrid laminate, the thermal strain of the metal ply is not affected by the moisture, and has no molecule chain elongation problem as the high polymer material. As a result, the curvatures of hybrid laminates have no obvious change even a long time after the manufacture process. Table 3 presents the measured curvatures of hybrid and pure bi-stable laminates at the 15th day after the manufacturing process. It indicates that the curvature keeping ability of hybrid laminates are much more improved than the pure unsymmetric laminates.

The critical loads to snap the bi-stable laminates are given in Table 4. The critical loads to snap the pure laminate is very small, which is the disadvantage of pure bi-stable laminates. The load-bearing capacity of pure composite laminates can be improved by increasing the thickness, but meanwhile the curvatures of stable shapes are decreased. In comparison, the critical load of hybrid composite laminate increases greatly (up to 10 times) due to the metal layer which enhances the laminates' stiffness. The hybridization over pure bi-stable composite laminates is able to accomplish both the high load-bearing capacity and the large shape change. Meanwhile, similar as their shape keeping ability, the load-bearing capacity of the hybrid laminates will not decrease much because of the residual stress relax in the polymer matrix. To validate that, the snap-through process of the hybrid laminate is simulated by FEM.

Table 4 Measured critical loads for different bistable laminates

No.	Size (mm ²)	Layups	Total thickness (mm)	Critical Loads (N)
1	300×100	[0 ₂ /M/90 ₂]	0.73	5.24
2	300×100	[0 ₂ /90 ₂]	0.50	0.56
3	300×100	0/90	0.25	0.23

The finite element models of the hybrid bi-stable laminates with the layup [0/st/90] and dimension 300×100mm are numerically generated during the cool-down process, see Fig.5. The load in vertical direction was applied to the central point of the laminate. In the simulation, an analytical plane is required to simulate the glass plate in the experiments. The surface-to-surface contact between the laminate model and the analytical plane is established to simulate the interaction between the specimen and the glass plate. The boundary and loads are shown in Fig.5, in which a friction force is applied at the right edge along horizontal direction.

Fig.5 The boundary and load for hybrid bi-stable laminate

The FEA on the prediction of the load carrying capacity is performed twice. The first time it is assumed that there is no stress relaxation in the polymer matrix of hybrid laminate. The second time it is assumed that the residual thermal stress in the polymer matrix is completely relaxed. The curves of load vs. curvature are potted in Fig.6. The largest load at the curve peak is the critical load of the hybrid laminate. The FEM predicted critical loads of hybrid laminates with and without residual stress in polymer matrix are 4.4 N and 3.5 N respectively. Without considering the thermal stress in polymer matrix, the critical load of hybrid laminate has a decrease of 20.4%. However, it is impossible that the residual thermal stress of the polymer matrix completely relaxes.

Therefore, the actual critical load reduction of hybrid laminate is much less than 20.4%. It is much more improved comparing with the critical load reduction of a pure unsymmetric laminate, which is often more than 60 % due to the moisture effect^[18].

Fig.6 Loads vs. curvatures curve during snap-through process of 300 × 100mm, [0/st/90] hybrid laminate

6. Conclusions

In conclusion, the hybrid bi-stable composite laminate are investigated comparing with the pure composite bi-stable laminates. The cured shapes were studied using the analytical model, FEM and experiments, and good agreements among them are observed. The FEA results indicate that the thermal strain of the metal ply contributes more on the bi-stability of the hybrid laminate. The hybridization provides more design freedoms to achieve required bi-stable laminates. Comparisons of cured shapes and critical loads between hybrid bi-stable laminates and pure composite laminates show that the hybridization enable to accomplish both the high load-bearing capacity and the large shape change. Further, the hybrid laminates have much more improved curvature keeping ability and critical load keeping ability than pure unsymmetric composite laminates in moisture circumstances.

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